

TWO DIFFERENT VIEWS ON JADIDS AND ITS CONSEQUENCES

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Abstract. This article describes the division of Jadids into two currents, the diversity of opinions between them, and the issues of mutual disagreement.

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The jadids were separated into two conflicting streams – the old-fashioned one and the youth led by Fitrat. As a result, a unity arose in which there was mutual disagreement. This situation gave rise to unorthodox actions. As a result, a peaceful protest to apply the Emir manifesto was persecuted and repression against the jadids began. F.Khojaev belongs to this macro youth group, and later remains in this position. The jadids differed from older generations in that they did not miscalculate the tactics of open exits [1]. Aynius suggests that "Fitrat and F.Due to the fact that the left group, led by khojaev, could not see far away and misunderstood the situation, the Jadid group was tormented. It should be recognized that although our respect and kindness to representatives of the young jadids Are Unlimited, the historical events of the following years show that Abdulvohid Burkhanov, Usman Zhuraev, Muhiddin ghafat, Moses Saidjonov, Sadriddin Ayniy and others correctly assessed the situation, the jadidists did not have influence and power among the main part of the population. The masses were influenced by the clergy and could rise against the jadids at any time at his urging. Therefore, they were extremely thoughtful, careful movements, in favor of gradual, gradual reforms without revolution, especially bloody conflicts. In fact, the initiators of the first manifesto, and then the Kolesov events were also leftist jadids in

a revolutionary mood, who were not afraid of an armed uprising. However, although the bukharians were curious, they tried not to allow the organization to secede. Abdulvohid Burkhanov was left as chairman of the organization. On the eve of the February bourgeois revolution, the faction of young bukharians will split into two groups. One of them was called "Old jadidists" [2]. He was led by Munzim. The second group, which had renamed itself the new young bukharians, was led by F.Khojaev, A.The fitratas were his benefactors. The purpose of both groups was to fight against the same emirate. One of this group followed the path of enlightenment and brilliance, while the other promoted panturkist, petty bourgeois ideas. After the February Revolution, an association takes place in both groups and a newly formed "Young Bukharan faction jury" is formed and headed by a central committee, with a central committee jury consisting of Mirzo Abdulvohid (chairman), Abdurauf Fitrat (Secretary), Usman Khojaev (treasurer), MK members Mukhiddin Rif'at, Musa Saidjonov, ATO Khojaev, Ahmadjan Abdulusaidov (Khamidi), Fayzullo Khojaev, Khamid Khojava. Hearing that Nicholas was overthrown by the Tsar, the young bukharians take the task of organizing protests, putting before Amir Olimkhan demands to reform the Emir's government, establish a constitutional state. In this regard, both groups promote the demand for Amir Olimkhan to issue a decree on the reform of the government (manifesto) [3]. On this issue, the head of the "old jadidists" Munzim and the leaders of the new group of young bukharians F.A disagreement arises between khojaev and Fitrat. A serious argument that goes between the two groups causes discord between the two groups. It is said that the Emir agrees to reform. But on the eve of the release of the Emir's decree aimed at deceiving avom, the representative of the new Provisional Government, Miller, represented the "old jadids" Uthman Khojaev (Usmankhoja Steelkhojaev), Mirzo Abdulvohid Munzim (Burkhanov) and representative F from the new group of young bukharians.He invites khojaev to his presence for communication. It is in this situation that Munzim and his

supporters, fully following the rules of secret proceedings, throw the following demands of young bukharians on this decree on Miller:

1. To give more authority to the people's representatives in the Emir's government and local stations and to establish popular control over the authorities;
2. Giving freedom to the press and education;
3. Replacing some ignorant governors with new ones.

At the same time, F. Another group of young bukharians, led by khojaev, will meet the February Revolution in Russia with time and gather at his house to celebrate the victory. The Society sent a congratulatory message to the Provisional Government through the Samarkand Telegraph asking for support in the issue of reform in the emirate of Bukhara [4]. The Emir, overcome by the onset of the liberation movement in the land, agrees to issue a decree and makes great false promises to the people. According to Ayni's testimony, "...In the preparation of the draft decree, no one from the representatives of the people or young bukharians was invited. Perhaps, on the night of his close friends, walking in the nuridids of Nicholas, the Miller, Shul'ga, and Wendensky, who had become bu-gun "erkiteers", were put in charge of the work of preparing the project." [5]

It is at this point that the spies of the emir and the servants of the secret police of the Provisional Government hesitate to torment all members of groups, societies and factions, to punish its active members. Munzim knew earlier that this would happen. Because, when he met Miller, he had his eye on the notebook in his hand, which contained a list of all the hypocritical, hurried-minded people, and in alphabetical order the first line was the sharifi of Ayni's name. It can be seen that Miller was a spy thrown into the young bukharians, who was tasked with obtaining information about the figures and activities of this movement and delivering it to the emirate.

On the 28th of jumodiussoni in khijriy 1335, melody on April 20, 1917, a solemn reception of Amir Olimkhan is held at the Rakhimjani hotel. In it, the decree on reform is read and read in the presence of scribes, nobles and young bukharians. Of the young

bukharians at the reception, only F. Khojaev will participate. At about three o'clock that day, some of the young bukharians gathered in the courtyard of a man named Ahmad Naim, and F.Khojaev, in his words, interprets the " decree of the Emir " as a great victory, a huge step towards the liberation of the disenfranchised Bukharan people. Ayniy writes by the representative of the Provisional Government Shul'ga, the publication of this decree of the emir and the state of the young bukharians of that time:

"Young bukharians would organize rallies and conventions all over the city after Friday prayers that day, recite, comment, and explain this mani-Fest to the people"[6].

This is what we know that after the announcement of the decree of the emir on the passage of reforms, Mirzo Muhiddin Mansurov, chairman of the Society of merchants of Bukhara, sent a telegram to the Emir, congratulating him and calling him the creator of the new era. Some of the young bukharians, including Abdurauf Fitrat, thanked Amir Olimkhan and the Russian Provisional Government in connection with this decree. Ahmad Naim court (1917 20 April) was attended by Munzim. After an argument between the team, along with Fazliddin Makhdum and Mukhiddin Mansurov, he opposes the holding of a farewell demonstration as a thank you to the Emir's decree (manifesto). On this issue, Young bukharians support him from the Central Committee of the faction ("old jadidists") – Mukhiddin Rifat, Moses Saidjonov and ahmadjan Makhdum Khamidi, Fazliddin Makhdum, Mirzo Izzatullo and other maslakids from the jadidism movement activists.

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